

**ASSESSING PINAS SARAP TV SHOW AS A TRAVEL MOTIVATION IN
PROMOTING THE FILIPINO CUISINES AS ANTICIPATED BY
SELECTED TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY MANAGEMENT
STUDENTS IN A UNIVERSITY LOCATED IN MANILA**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 9

Pages: 1436-1441

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2923

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14652425

Manuscript Accepted: 12-20-2024

Assessing Pinas Sarap TV Show as a Travel Motivation in Promoting the Filipino Cuisines as Anticipated by Selected Tourism and Hospitality Management Students in a University Located in Manila

Apolinar P. Datu,* Julius R. Beltran, Rossana B. Liray, Rommel H. Orquiza, Christopher T. Takano
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study explores the role of the Pinas Sarap TV show as a travel motivation tool in promoting Filipino cuisine, as perceived by selected Tourism and Hospitality Management students at a private university in Manila. It investigates how the program influences various factors in travel, including accessibility, attractions, culture, education, and gastronomy. A descriptive quantitative research design was employed where there were 60 respondents in this study. Data were collected through a survey questionnaire. The statistical methods employed in this study were the percentage, weighted mean, and T-test used to analyze the findings. The results indicate that Pinas Sarap motivates viewers to explore Filipino gastronomy and travel destinations. Respondents reported a higher motivational level after watching the show, particularly in seeking cultural knowledge, experiencing authentic cuisines, and appreciating the history of Filipino food. There was also a notable impact on their awareness of food-related travel opportunities, with a significant difference observed in travel motivations before and after viewing the program. The study underscores the potential of culinary travel shows as effective mediums for boosting local tourism. It recommends further investment in such programs to enhance their reach and influence, ultimately supporting the promotion of local destinations and cuisines. Future researchers are encouraged to examine the impact of other digital platforms, such as blogs and travel documentaries, on tourism development.

Keywords: *travel motivation, gastronomy tourism, culinary tourism, Filipino cuisines*

Introduction

Most travel programs primarily focus on documentaries, which provide knowledge and information regarding specific societal issues and topics. However, reality variety programs combine variety, reality, and fiction; travel programs, which combine seeking fun and entertainment, have developed into a significant genre known as "travel entertainment." According to reports, changes in travel programs are causing changes in travel pursuit and tourist trends—furthermore, credit card usage for travel and leisure increases after travel reality-variety shows are broadcast.

According to the University of Central Florida (2021), food tourism, also known as culinary tourism or gastronomy tourism, is the practice of people who look for gastronomic experiences to deepen their understanding of a country or way of life while visiting. Traveling with culinary tourists broadens their horizons and teaches them about the connection between local cuisine and traditions. They seek genuine gastronomic encounters that expose them to novel tastes, textures, and customs.

Food tourism has increased due to food television programs and social media, affecting nearby businesses. Consequently, the demand for individuals with prior expertise in the hotel sector is expanding. According to the University of Central Florida (2021), the growing needs are being exacerbated by businesses in the food and beverage sector and regional and federal governments attempting to promote food tourism.

Research Questions

This study will be conducted to evaluate the influence of Pinas Sarap TV Show as motivation in promoting Filipino Cuisine. Specifically, this study intends to answer the following questions:

1. What are the profiles of the respondents in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. program;
 - 1.2. age; and
 - 1.3. gender?
2. What is the degree of influence by TV Show to the different factor in travelling in terms of:
 - 2.1. accessibility;
 - 2.2. attraction;
 - 2.3. culture;
 - 2.4. education; and
 - 2.5. gastronomy?
3. What is the motivational level of the respondents before and after watching Pinas Sarap?
4. Is there an importance in the level of influence by the respondents to travel after watching Pinas Sarap?
5. On the basis on the findings of the study, what are beneficial recommendations should the researcher suggest for the tourist

who are looking to taste Filipino Cuisines?

Literature Review

Tan (2021) asserts culinary tourism is essential to contemporary travel and directly impacts a nation's economy and hospitality sector. Their cuisine culture should be developed in order to support the expanding culinary tourist trend. A taste trekker welcomes that people from diverse ethnic origins consume different cuisines and is keen to discover more about other cultures and their culinary traditions.

According to Kara and Mkwizu (2020), travel motivation is viewed as an internal force that arouses and pushes an individual from choosing a particular destination with the intention of getting the desired benefits and satisfaction (Pyo et al., 1989; Yoon and Uysal, 2005). Motivation is viewed as a sociopsychological factor that pushes an individual to a new destination and takes part in leisure activities (Iso-Ahola, 1982; Beard and Ragheb, 1983). According to this study, a traveler's intrinsic motivation is what propels them to go to Tanzania for a leisure trip.

Roaldsen et. al. (2020), food is much more than functionality. Food and culinary experiences are increasingly seen as crucial for drawing tourists since they are also a way for a community and its citizens to express themselves. Local cuisine is seen as an even more alluring culinary experience since it is associated with a location and possesses other qualities like being authentic and short-distance. An overview of the literature on local cuisine in the tourism literature and related study domains is given by this systematic meta-literature review, which poses the following questions:

According to Carlos et. al., (2021), TV series have become one of the most successful types of audio-visual product. They are a great way to promote the locations they portray, portray them as alluring travel destinations, and create the phenomena known as "film tourism" because of their capacity to generate sizable, devoted audiences. The goal of the current study is to clarify the factors that influence viewers' choices to travel to a place they have seen in a television show. More precisely, destination awareness and visit motivation—two factors recognized as antecedents of travel decisions—were taken into account.

Local Literature

According to Moran (2020), One of the industries that successfully continues to find ways for Filipinos to travel and experience more of our country is tourism, The Department of Tourism (DOT) invited foodies to embark on "Food Trips" in the second leg of its virtual Kain Na! Food and Travel Festival 2020 last Nov. 3 to 6. "Food has always been one of the Filipino's travel motivations," DOT Secretary Bernadette Romulo-Puyat said at the opening salvo. "And, as we slowly but surely reopen more and more tourist destinations, let us keep our appetite for 'food trips' with the exciting online offerings of Kain Na! 2020."

According to Parilla (2020), the Philippine archipelago has a lot to offer to its local and to the tourists – from its scenic mountain to its panoramic view of cobalt beaches and in between.

Methodology

Research Design

Quantitative research aims to figure out how many people act, think, or feel in a certain way. It is a systematic analysis of events based on gathered measurable data and the application of computational, mathematical, or statistical tools. Large sample sizes were used in this research, with a focus on the number of responses rather than the more focused or emotional insight. The researchers can address the similarities and differences of the variables utilizing a comparative study. It will be used as the foundation of the data needed to answer the study's concerns with rational, objective-wise conclusions and recommendations by recognizing both distinctions and similarities of stated variables.

Respondents

The researchers used descriptive method and quantitative analysis in Assessing Pinas Sarap Tv Show as A Travel Motivation in Promoting the Filipino Cuisines As perceived by Selected Tourism and Hospitality Management Students of a Private University located in Manila. A total of 60 students from Tourism and Hospitality Management served as the respondents.

Instrument

The researchers gathered the data using a survey questionnaire created with Microsoft Office Forms. The demographics of the respondents will be the first part of the survey, including their Program, Age, and Gender. The other part includes 35 questions done by researchers to determine the effectiveness of the Pinas Sarap TV Show as a Travel Motivation. The survey was done online, which was one of the most efficient ways to collect data without having to use the traditional approach of handling out survey questionnaires.

Procedure

The data was conducted through online platform using Microsoft Office Forms. There were 60 respondents came from the Tourism and Hospitality Management students at a Private University Located in Manila under the College of Tourism and Hospitality Management.

Questionnaires was created to answer the problem stated in the content under Statement of the Problem. the statistics formula of percentage, weighted mean, and T-test was utilized by the researchers. The T-test was utilized to answer problem number 4 regarding the difference level of influence of before and after watching Pinas Sarap TV Show.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers seek permission from the respondents if they can answer the questions in their convenient time and rest assured that all information will be kept confidentially and will be used for the research purposes only.

Results and Discussion

This research presents the outcome of the fundings based on the questions answered by the respondents. The results are presented based on the emergent themes, sub-themes, core ideas, and categorization.

Table 1.1. *Demographic profile of the respondents in terms age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
26-27	1	2%
24-25	2	3%
22-23	19	32%
20-21	35	58%
18-19	3	5%
Total	60	100%

Table 1.1 illustrates the profile of the respondents in terms of their age. The table above shows that the age bracket 20-21 got the highest frequency of 35 or 58%. Next was age bracket 22-23 with a frequency of 19 or 32%. Third was age bracket 18-19 with a frequency of 3 or 5%. Followed by age group 24-25 with a frequency of 3%. The last age group who got the least frequency was 26-27 with 1 or 2%.

Table 1.2. *Demographic profile of the respondents in gender*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	12	20%
Female	48	80%
Total	60	100%

Table 1.2 illustrates the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of their gender. It seems that most respondents were Female that got the highest frequency of 48 or 80%. And the lowest frequency of 12 or 20% belong to Male category.

Table 1.3 *Demographic profile of the respondents in program*

<i>Program</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Bstm	35	58%
Bshm	25	42%
Total	60	100%

Table 1.3 illustrates the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of their program. The table above shows that the Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management students got the highest frequency of 35 or 58%., while the frequency of 25 or 42% falls under the Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management.

Table 2.1. *Level of influence of TV Show to the different factor in travelling in terms of accessibility*

<i>Accessibility</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. Whenever I travel, I always want to go to the places where it is easily accessible.	3.62	Strongly Agree
2. Whenever I travel, I always consider if the place has an open space.	3.57	Strongly Agree
3. Whenever I travel, I prefer the route/road of the place has traffic signage so that I won't be lost.	3.50	Strongly Agree
Composite Weighted Mean	3.56	Strongly Agree

Table 2.1 illustrates the weighted mean of the respondents, and verbal interpretation of level of influence of TV Show to the different factor in travelling in terms of accessibility.

It revealed that statement number 1 to 3 got a result of Strongly Agree that means all can be considered as a way in which tourist look for ways on how they could go to a place for them to taste Filipino Cuisines.

Table 2.2 illustrates that the weighted mean of the responses and verbal interpretation of level of influence of TV show to the different factor in travelling in terms of attractions. It revealed that the statement number 1 to 3 explains how tourist look for attractions for them to be able to see the beauty of the scenery which is strongly agreed by the respondents

Table 2.2. Level of influence of TV Show to the different factor in travelling in terms of attractions

Attractions	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Whenever I travel, I prefer places where I can engage to beautiful attractions.	3.87	Strongly Agree
2. Whenever I travel, I follow the rules and regulations of the place to preserve the natural environment.	3.80	Strongly Agree
3. Whenever I travel, I want to recommend the attraction that I experienced to my family and friends.	3.80	Strongly Agree
Composite Weighted Mean	3.82	Strongly Agree

Table 2.3 illustrates that the weighted mean of the responses and verbal interpretation of level of influence of TV show to the different factor in travelling in terms of culture.

Table 2.3 Level of influence of TV Show to the different factor in travelling in terms of culture

Culture	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Whenever I travel, I want to socialize to the locals to experience their culture.	3.53	Strongly Agree
2. Whenever I travel, I want to know their different customs, rituals, and lifestyle.	3.57	Strongly Agree
3. Whenever I travel, I want to gain knowledge about the history of the place.	3.53	Strongly Agree
Composite Weighted Mean	3.54	Strongly Agree

It revealed that the statement 2 which was “Whenever I travel, I want to know their different customs, rituals and lifestyle” got the highest weighted mean of 3.57 with a verbal interpretation of strongly agree.

Table 2.4. Level of influence of TV Show to the different factor in travelling in terms of education

Education	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Whenever I travel, I want to go to the place where the TV show is conducted.	3.12	Agree
2. Whenever I travel, I want to use the knowledge that I gained from the place to enhance my skill.	3.68	Strongly Agree
3. Whenever I travel, I want to learn something that I haven't learned inside the classroom.	3.57	Strongly Agree
Composite Weighted Mean	3.46	Strongly Agree

Table 2.4 illustrates that the weighted mean of the responses and verbal interpretation of level of influence of TV Show to the different factor in travelling in terms of education. It revealed that statement number 2 which was “Whenever I travel, I want to use the knowledge that I gained from the place to enhance my skill” got the highest weighted mean of 3.68 with verbal interpretation of strongly agree.

Table 2.5. Level of influence of TV Show to the different factor in travelling in terms of gastronomy

Gastronomy	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Whenever I travel, I prefer going to the places where the famous food is served.	3.55	Strongly Agree
2. Whenever I travel, I want to try the different traditional food.	3.55	Strongly Agree
3. The more I know about the food, the more I want to experience it.	3.73	Strongly Agree
Composite Weighted Mean	3.61	Strongly Agree

Table 2.5 illustrates that the weighted mean of the responses and verbal interpretation of level of influence of TV Show to the different factor in travelling in terms of gastronomy. It revealed that statement number 3 which was “The more I know about the food, the more I want to experience it” got the highest weighted mean of 3.73 with verbal interpretation of strongly agree.

Table 3.1. Motivational level of the respondents before watching Pinas Sarap

Motivational Level Of The Respondents Before Watching Pinas Sarap	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am motivated to travel to different places to experience different types of food.	3.53	Strongly Agree
2. I am not aware of the places who serves a specific kind of food.	3.07	Agree
3. I am motivated to travel because I am curious about the different food cultures and places.	3.52	Strongly Agree
4. I am motivated to visit different food tourism destinations to experience the specific food.	3.83	Strongly Agree
5. I am motivated to visit different places to understand the different types of food that involve certain cooking practices.	3.37	Strongly Agree
6. I want to recommend travel places that offer a variety of foods to my family and friends.	3.55	Strongly Agree

7.	I want to appreciate the Filipino food history.	3.78	Strongly Agree
8.	I want to increase my knowledge about the places who offers different kinds of food.	3.63	Strongly Agree
9.	I want to discover new types of condiments and ingredients from other places.	3.55	Strongly Agree
10.	I want to recommend travel places that offer a variety of foods to my family and friends.	3.51	Strongly Agree
Composite Weighted Mean		3.53	Strongly Agree

Table 3.1 illustrates that the weighted mean of the responses and verbal interpretation of motivational level of the respondents before watching Pinas Sarap. It revealed that statement number 4, “I am motivated to visit different food tourism destinations to experience the specific food” got the highest weighted mean of 3.83 with verbal interpretation of strongly agree. Followed by statement number 7, “I want to appreciate the Filipino food history” got the highest weighted mean of 3.78 with verbal interpretation of strongly agree. Followed by statement number 8, “I want to increase my knowledge about the places who offers different kinds of food” got a weighted mean of 3.63 with verbal interpretation of strongly agree.

Table 3.1. *Motivational level of the respondents after watching Pinas Sarap*

<i>Motivational Level Of The Respondents After Watching Pinas Sarap</i>		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1.	After watching Pinas Sarap, it motivates me to travel to different places to experience different types of food.	3.70	Strongly Agree
2.	After watching Pinas Sarap, it gave me an idea that there are many places where I can travel for food.	3.70	Strongly Agree
3.	After watching Pinas Sarap, I realized that we have many different places that has a different culture of food.	3.73	Strongly Agree
4.	After watching an episode, it gave me an idea where to travel next to experience the specific food that they showed.	3.65	Strongly Agree
5.	After watching Pinas Sarap, it made me understand that different types of food involve certain cooking practices.	3.63	Strongly Agree
6.	After watching Pinas Sarap, I will recommend this TV Show to my family and friends to be informed about different travel destination that offers variety of foods.	3.55	Strongly Agree
7.	After watching Pinas Sarap, I appreciated the Filipino food history.	3.67	Strongly Agree
8.	After watching Pinas Sarap, it increases my knowledge about the Filipino history.	3.60	Strongly Agree
9.	After watching Pinas Sarap, I have newly discovered the different types of ingredients and condiments from other places.	3.58	Strongly Agree
10.	After watching Pinas Sarap, will recommend this TV Show to my family and friends to be informed about different travel destination that offers variety of foods.	3.52	Strongly Agree
Composite Weighted Mean		3.63	Strongly Agree

Table 3.2 illustrates that the weighted mean of the responses and verbal interpretation of the motivational level of respondents after watching Pinas Sarap. It revealed that statement number 3 which was “After watching Pinas Sarap, I realized that we have many different places that has a different culture of food.” got the highest weighted mean of 3.73 with a verbal interpretation of strongly agree.

Table 4. *Significant difference in the level of influence of the respondents to travel after watching Pinas Sarap*

<i>Computed t</i>	<i>Level of Significance</i>	<i>Degree of Freedom</i>	<i>Critical t</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Description</i>
3.04	0.05	59	2.01	Reject H0	Significant

The table above illustrates the data above that, the computed t of 3.04 is greater than the critical value of 2.001 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. This showed that there was a significant difference between the level of influence of the respondents to travel after watching Pinas Sarap. This showed that there was impact to the level of influence to travel after watching Pinas Sarap.

Conclusions

Based on the summary of the results, traveling is considered as decision-making of where and which most of the tourist expectations and needs are satisfied and that there are standards considered by tourists. TV shows such as Pinas Sarap are one of the best mediums to cater to those factors tourists are looking to. It showcased a place's origin, history, delicacies, culture, and attraction. Instead of manually searching blogs, reading articles, or waiting for someone's recommendation, we can instead watch such TV show segments to experience traveling virtually.

The level of influence of TV show of is strongly high as the respondents strongly agreed with all the statements.

The motivational level of the of the respondents before watching Pinas Sarap is strongly high as the respondents strongly agreed with all the statements.

The motivational level of the of the respondents after watching Pinas Sarap is strongly high as the respondents strongly agreed with all the statements.

Based on the computation of the test difference between the motivational level of the respondents before and after watching Pinas Sarap of the Respondents, there is a significant difference between the two variables.

Students should explore informative documentaries or TV shows to learn more about what different places can offer in terms of travelling.

The future researchers should study how blogs, travel documentaries are beneficial to the locals.

For DOT, Department of Tourism can invest to different kinds of TV Shows or platform that can boost local tourism, by that, tourist will have more interest and be encouraged to prioritize local destinations.

References

- Buiza, F., Campos, E., Garcia, L., & Prieto, L. (2021). The Gastronomic Experience: Motivation and Satisfaction of the Gastronomic Tourist—The Case of Puno City (Peru). Retrieved From <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/13/16/9170/htm>
- Carlos, P., Brea, J., & Vila, N. (2021). Film tourism in Spain: Destination awareness and visit motivation as determinants to visit places seen in TV series. Science Direct. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2444883420303168>
- Jordstad, M., Ljunggren, E., & Roaldsen, I. (2020). Local Food in Tourism: A Systematic Literature Review. ResearchGate. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340888664_Local_Food_in_Tourism_A_Systematic_Literature_Review
- Kim, B., & Kim, O. (2020). Relationship between Viewing Motivation, Presence, Viewing Satisfaction, and Attitude toward Tourism Destinations Based on TV Travel Reality Variety Programs. mdpi. Retrieved from <https://www.mdpi.com/735266>
- Mkwizu, N.S. (2020). Demographic factors and travel motivation among leisure tourists in Tanzania. emerald insight. Retrieved from <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IHR-01-2020-0002/full/html#sec002>
- Parilla, E. (2020). A study on customer awareness and satisfaction level towards food tourism at Adams Ilocos Norte, Philippines. Sees Candies. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344396081_A_study_on_customer_awareness_and_satisfaction_level_towards_food_tourism_at_Adams_Ilocos_Norte_Philippines
- Tan, D. (2021). Culinary Tourism, Now Trending. Le Cordon Bleu. Retrieved from <https://www.cordonbleu.edu/news/culinary-tourism/en> University of Central Florida (2021). Food Tourism: The Impact of Food TV Shows on Local Industries. UCF ONLINE. Retrieved from <https://www.ucf.edu/online/hospitality/news/food-tourism/>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Apolinar P. Datu

National University – Philippines

Julius R. Beltran

National University – Philippines

Rossana B. Liray

National University – Philippines

Rommel H. Orquiza

Philippines

Christopher T. Takano

ICCT Colleges – Philippines